

Chemoresistive SO₂ gas sensor with improved sensing performances by modification of copper hexacyanoferrate to PANI/SnO₂

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Abstract- To improve the sensing performances of chemoresistive SO₂ gas sensor, we prepared PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF electrode by the in-situ synthesis method. The prepared PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF electrode exhibited high linearity for SO₂ in the range of 0-100 ppm, response time of 20 s, recovery time of 40 s, and good reproducibility. The comparison of the sensing performances of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF and PANI/SnO₂ electrodes confirmed that PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF performed better than PANI/SnO₂ in terms of the reproducibility, linearity and selectivity.

Keywords: chemoresistive sensor, sulfur dioxide, polyaniline, copper hexacyanoferrate.

I. INTRODUCTION

SO₂ is a major waste gas emitted by metal plants such as iron works, steel plants and smelting plants and various chemical plants. Sulfur dioxide not only causes direct damage to the respiratory organs of the human [1] due to air pollution but also causes acid rain, which affects the environment by reducing the pH of the lakes, lagoons and soils [2-4]. Therefore, it is very important to measure the concentration of sulfur dioxide in the atmosphere accurately and to limit the emission strictly.

Hence, many kinds of sensors for the measurement of sulfur dioxide concentration have been developed based on different techniques, [5-7] among which the chemoresistive sensors have the advantages of low cost, simple fabrication process, small size, long life, fast response and so on. [8]

Commonly, the chemoresistive sensors are made from two materials: organic conducting polymers and semiconductor metal oxides. [8] We can use the materials such as polyaniline (PANI), poly (3, 4-ethylene-dioxythiophene) (PEDOT), polypyrrole (PPy), polythiophene (PT) and so on as an organic conducting polymer. Among them, polyaniline (PANI) is one of the most widely used materials because of its ease of synthesis and the ability to detect various gases. [9, 10] And the semiconductor metal oxides such as WO₃, ZnO, SnO₂, TiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and SiO₂ can be used. [11] Among them, SnO₂ is the

most widely used material for many kinds of harmful gas sensing. [12]

However, the gas sensor using PANI alone has the disadvantage of poor reproducibility, selectivity and stability due to the influence of volatile organic compounds and moisture present in the atmosphere. [7, 13] In addition, the gas sensor using only SnO₂ operates at high temperatures (300-400 °C), resulting in degradation of the sensing materials and changes of the baseline by the assay. [14, 15]

To overcome these limitations, a gas sensor with improved sensitivity and operability at room temperature was fabricated by combining PANI and SnO₂. For example, Betty [16] fabricated the sensitive SO₂ sensor using PANI/SnO₂.

However, the PANI/SnO₂ sensor has the disadvantage of having a poor selectivity like the other chemoresistive sensors. For example, according to S. K. Shukla and et al. [17], PANI/SnO₂ nanocomposites were prepared in thin film form to prepare humidity sensors. And, PANI/SnO₂ sensor prepared by C. Murugan and et al [18] was sensitive to benzene and toluene vapor.

Hongyan Xu [19] used PANI/SnO₂ composites for sensing NO₂. L. Geng and co-researchers reported that the PANI/SnO₂ thin film sensor prepared by the hydrothermal method exhibited excellent sensing performances for ethanol and acetone. [20] As

shown above, PANI/SnO₂ composites have the response characteristics for various kinds of gases. Therefore, further improvement of the sensing performances of PANI/SnO₂ is needed.

In general, the third component is modified in PANI/SnO₂ to improve the sensing performance of PANI/SnO₂-based sensors. Saravanan and co-researchers had fabricated the PANI/SnO₂ and PANI/SnO₂/rGO ternary composites by facile one-step hydrothermal approach followed by polymerization method to improve the sensing performances for H₂S and NH₃. [21] G.D. Khuspe and co-researchers deposited the PANI-SnO₂ nanocomposite based thin films doped with 10-50 wet % camphor sulfonic acid (CSA) on the glass substrates using the spin coating technique to prepare the NH₃ sensor with improved significant sensitivity (91%) towards 100ppm NH₃ operating at room temperature. [22]

Luo and co-researchers reported that a light assisted SO₂ gas sensor based on polyaniline (PANI) and Ag nanoparticle co-modified tin dioxide nanostructures (Ag/PANI/SnO₂) exhibited the significant SO₂ sensitivity and excellent recovery properties. [23] However, when the concentration of sulfide gas increase upon the limit, due to the formation of an Ag₂S at the electrode surface of the Ag-based sensors, the sensor is deteriorated irreversibly changing its characteristic value.

Therefore, further studies regarding the selectivity improvement of PANI/SnO₂ based SO₂ sensors are needed.

Hexacyanoferrate (CuHCF) can be used as an intermediate that can selectively react with SO₂. CuHCF is a frequently used material for enhancing the selectivity of an electrochemical sensor. D. Ravi Shankaran and et al. [24] reported on a copper hexacyanoferrate-mediated electrochemical sulfur dioxide gas sensor. According to their report, that sensor was highly selective because it was based on the selective reaction between the CuHCF and sulfur dioxide.

Some researchers tried to modify hexacyanoferrate to a chemoresistive sensor using this property to improve the sensor performance. Pui Kee Lee et al. [25] prepared CuHCF-PPy composite films and used it as nicotine sensors. They deposited directly the CuHCF-PPy nanocomposite on reduced graphene oxide (rGO) by a direct self-assembly technique for the first time. Also, the use of iron hexacyanoferrate, known as Prussian blue, for the preparation of PB-PPy nanocomposites as a sensing material has been reported. [26]

In this paper, we have investigated the modification of copper hexacyanoferrate on PANI/SnO₂ nanocomposites to improve the sensing performances of chemoresistive SO₂ sensors.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Chemicals

Aniline (C₆H₇N, Sigma-Aldrich, >99.5%), SnO₂ (~325 mesh, Sigma-Aldrich), ammonium persulfate (APS, Merck), copper nitrate hexahydrate (Cu(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Aladdin), potassium hexacyanoferrate (K₃[Fe(CN)₆], analytical grade, Aladdin), sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS, analytical grade, Sigma-Aldrich), HCl (35%, Shanghai) and absolute ethanol(Shanghai) were used without the further purification. Deionized water was used in all experiments.

Preparation of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF sensing electrode

Fig. 1 shows the manufacturing process of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF sensing electrode.

Figure 1: Manufacturing process flow diagram of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF sensing electrode

Pretreatment of substrate material

Printed Circuit Board (PCB, 20 mm × 10 mm × 1 mm) with an interdigital electrode were used as a substrate material for sensor fabrication.

Before the formation of a sensing thin film on the substrate, we have to pretreatment the substrate. The pretreatment proceed was similar to the pretreatment method described in ref. [27]. To remove impurities on the PCB substrate, 50 mL of 0.5% aqueous solution of the non-ionic surfactant - SDBS was placed and washed at 50 °C for 15 min and then immersed in 1 M HCl solution for 60 min. Then, it was washed once with hot water (50 °C) for 3 min and three times with cold water for 3 min. Then, ultrasonic dispersion was performed for 30 min in an absolute ethanol. The cleaned substrates were dried at 60 °C for 1 h.

Preparation of copper hexacyanoferrate [28]

0.1 M $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and 0.1 M $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ solutions were prepared, respectively. 90mL of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution was placed into 250 mL beaker and 60 mL of $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ solution was slowly dropped under the magnetic stirring. In that time, CuHCF particles were formed.

$3\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + 2\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = \text{Cu}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_2 + 6\text{KNO}_3$
The resulting powder was separated by filtration and washed five times with 100 mL of deionized water to remove the unreacted materials. Then the powder was dried at 60°C for 24 h.

Preparation of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF modified electrode

250 mL beaker was filled with 100 mL of 0.5 M HCl solution, and 2 g of aniline monomer was slowly added, followed by magnetic stirring to form a homogeneous solution. Then, 0.2 g of SnO₂ nanopowder and 0.4 g of CuHCF powder added to the solution and ultrasonically dispersed for 30 min. The resulting SnO₂ - CuHCF dispersed aniline-HCl solution was magnetically stirred in an ice water bath at 0 ~ 5 °C, and the pretreated substrate was immersed and slowly dropped 2.5 g of 0.5 M aqueous APS solution. At that time, the reaction temperature should be kept at 0~5°C. The stirring was allowed to proceed for 4 h. As a result of the

reaction, a dark green film was deposited on the substrate. The obtained sensing electrode was washed five times with the deionized water and dried at room temperature for 24 h.

Preparation of PANI/SnO₂ electrodes

The PANI/SnO₂ electrode was prepared according to the same procedure as above except for the addition of CuHCF powder.

Characterization and gas sensing performance tests

Characterization

The crystalline structures were investigated by Philips X-ray diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406^\circ$). In addition, FTIR spectra were recorded in the KBr phase with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} in the range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} using the Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, NICOLET IS20, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Finally, the spectroscopy analysis was carried out using the scanning electron microscopy (SEM, S-4800, Hitachi).

Gas sensing performance test

To perform the gas sensing performance test of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF sensing electrode, an experimental setup as shown in Fig. 2 was constructed.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the gas sensing test apparatus.

The gas sensing performances of PANI/SnO₂ and PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF electrodes were compared. The responses of the prepared sensing electrodes were defined as R_a/R_g as well as other chemoresistive sensors. Here, R_a represented the resistance of the sensor in clean air and R_g indicated the resistance of the sensor in the sample gas.

Cross-sensitivity for the interfering gases was evaluated using H₂S, NH₃, CO, C₂H₅OH, and acetone gases. During the experiments, the gas concentration, temperature and relative humidity were kept at 10 ppm, 25 °C and 60%, respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization

Fig. 3 shows the XRD spectra of PANI-SnO₂-CuHCF composite. The characteristic peaks of PANI at 14.9, 20.5 and 25.8°, SnO₂ at 26, 33, 37 and 50° and CuHCF at 17.3° are formed. XRD spectra showed that PANI-SnO₂-CuHCF was synthesized correctly. [29-31]

The characteristic peaks of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF composites were found at 2090.41, 1568.23, 1489.59, 1295.67, 1121.35, 793.21, 620.35 and 589.12 cm⁻¹. The peaks at 1568.23 and 1489.59 cm⁻¹ correspond to the C=C stretching vibrations of the benzene ring and the quinoid ring, respectively. [32] The peaks at 1295.67 cm⁻¹ and 793.21 cm⁻¹ resulted from the stretching vibration of the C-N and C-H bonds of the secondary aromatic amines, respectively. [33] The peaks of 620.35 and 589.12 cm⁻¹ correspond to the Sn-O-Sn vibration and Sn-O vibration of SnO₂. [34] The characteristic peak at 2090.41 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the Fe²⁺ - CN⁻-Fe³⁺ of CuHCF. [35-37] Sn-O-Sn vibration and Sn-O vibration of SnO₂. [34] The characteristic peak at 2090.41 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the Fe²⁺ - CN⁻-Fe³⁺ of CuHCF. [35-37]

Figure 3: XRD spectra of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF composite

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF composite

Fig. 5 shows the surface morphology of the CuHCF powder and PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF modified electrode, confirmed using the scanning electron microscopy (SEM, S-4800, Hitachi). It can be seen from the images that the conductive PANI film formed the continuous phase on the substrate and the SnO₂ particles and CuHCF powders were distributed relatively evenly, forming a rough surface. This structure is favorable for the adsorption of sample gases and the transfer of electrons during the reaction.

(a)

Fig. 4 shows the Fourier transform infrared spectra of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF composite.

(b)

Figure 5: SEM images of CuHCF powder (a) and PANI/SnO2/CuHCF modified electrode surface (b).

Gas sensing performance

• **Reproducibility**

Fig. 6 shows the resistance change characteristics of PANI/SnO2/CuHCF modified electrode and PANI/SnO2 electrode when the process of injecting and removing SO2 gas with a concentration of 10 ppm was repeated several times.

The initial resistance of PANI/SnO2/CuHCF electrode in the clean air was about 30MΩ, and decreased to about 11.5MΩ when it was exposed to 10 ppm SO2 gas. This is because the carrier concentration increases by the electrons generated from the reaction between SO2 and CuHCF. Moreover, SO2 is a reducing gas, and therefore, it reacts with the excess oxygen on the surface during the physical and chemical adsorption on the sensor surface, reducing the surface electron depletion, thereby increasing the surface electrical conductivity.

Figure 6: Reproducibility of PANI/SnO2/CuHCF modified electrode for SO2 gas

From Fig. 6, it can be seen that the response time of PANI/SnO2/CuHCF sensor is 20s, recovery time is about 40 s, and the reproducibility is relatively high. However, the PANI/SnO2 sensor had a response time of 25 s and it was fast, but a recovery time was 80 s which was relatively slow.

Linearity

Figs. 7 shows the response of PANI/SnO2/CuHCF modified electrode with SO2 concentration. From Fig. 7, it can be seen that PANI/SnO2/CuHCF modified electrode provides an excellent linearity in the range of 0-100 ppm.

Figure 7: Response of PANI/SnO2/CuHCF modified electrode to SO2 concentration

This can be explained by the limited number of active adsorption sites on the sensing electrode surface and the concentration of CuHCF, so that the reaction on the electrode surface does not proceed in proportion to the concentration of SO2.

Selectivity

Fig. 8 shows the selectivity of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF modified electrode and PANI/SnO₂ electrode. The most typical interfering gases in the use of SO₂ sensors are the reducing gases such as H₂S, NH₃, CO, C₂H₅OH, (CH₃)₂CO and so on. In this experiment, the concentration of each gas was fixed at 10 ppm. The temperature and humidity of the sensing chamber were also maintained at 25°C and 60 RH%.

Figure 8: Selectivity of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF modified electrode and PANI/SnO₂ electrode

In general, SO₂ sensors are sensitive to the other gases containing sulfur. It is because sulfur have the various oxidation number and sulfur-containing gases are oxidized or reduced according to the similar mechanisms.

In our experiments, the PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF modified electrode was only affected by the interference from H₂S and hardly responded to the other gases. However, the PANI/SnO₂ electrode showed a response for the almost all the gases mentioned above. This means that the selectivity to the sulfur-containing gases was greatly improved by CuHCF for PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF modified electrode.

The results showed that PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF modified electrode exhibited higher selectivity compared to PANI/SnO₂ electrode.

III. CONCLUSION

In this work, we fabricated PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF modified electrodes by the in-situ polymerization to

overcome the low selectivity of PANI/SnO₂ sensor. The comparison of the sensing performances of PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF and PANI/SnO₂ electrodes confirmed that PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF electrode performed better than PANI/SnO₂ electrode in terms of the reproducibility, linearity and selectivity. The PANI/SnO₂/CuHCF electrode exhibited excellent response characters with the high linearity, reproducibility and selectivity for SO₂ gas in the range of 0-100 ppm, demonstrated its potential as an environmental monitoring and personal protective sensor.

In the future, we will carry out the additional studies to further improve the mechanical properties and sensitivity of the sensing electrode by changing the substrate material, electrode preparation method, etc.

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